

Software Process Improvement Measurement And Evaluation Framework (SPI-MEF)

Today's Challenges in SPI Evaluations

With the increasing importance of software in industry and as well as in our everyday's life, the process of developing software has also gained significant importance. Many companies are investing large sums of money in improving their software processes through different Software Process Improvement (SPI) initiatives.

SPI initiatives are all software engineering methods or activities which are intended to improve the performance of the software process and these can be categorized into frameworks (e.g. CMM, CMMI, SPICE, QIP, Six Sigma, etc.), software engineering practices (e.g. inspections, test-driven development, etc.) or tools that support software engineering practices. After the undertaking of such SPI initiatives, it is of major interest for organizations to evaluate whether the investment for the improvement pays off.

The evaluation of SPI initiatives is a complex undertaking because there are various aspects that need to be taken into consideration.

Firstly, there is no common understanding on what needs to be measured for evaluating different success indicators (e.g. productivity, product quality, etc.) of improvement.

Secondly, the success of improvement initiatives is often primarily based on the evaluation of project outcomes without considering farther reaching ramifications. Consequently, the evaluation of improvement initiatives is too narrow and doesn't provide enough insight to validate their efficiency and effectiveness.

Thirdly, it is important to provide appropriate visibility of the evaluation results and evidence of improvement to the participating stakeholders of the initiative.

Need For SPI Evaluations

The evaluation of SPI through formal assessments like CBA-IPI, SCAMPI or other well-known assessments are concerned about determining the capability level of the organizational process by means of investigating its adherence to certain standards and identifying strengths and weakness in the process for suggesting areas for improvement.

The evaluation we are concerned about is different from these assessments. The concepts proposed in SPI-MEF promote an evaluation which considers the improvement from different perspectives and, in sum, increases the visibility, and consequentially alleviates the assessment of the achieved benefits.

Since the evaluation of the outcome of SPI initiative is complex but also crucial to the organization, there is a need for a measurement and evaluation framework to evaluate the outcome of SPI initiatives. In the current state-of-the-art, there is no framework specifically designed to carry out the evaluation of SPI initiatives' outcome. SPI-MEF tries to address this gap.

SPI-MEF Approach

- Enable organization to justify the investment on SPI by providing a measurement and evaluation framework for the systematic assessment of SPI initiatives.
- Provide a balanced view of the impact of SPI initiatives for a holistic evaluation by considering the five measurable entities in a software organization (Process, Project, Product, Organization and External).
- Increase the visibility of the results of the improvement for all stakeholders according to their specific needs.
- Reuse of same generic framework in evaluating a broad spectrum of SPI initiative since the framework is independent of specific SPI initiative.
- Provide an evolutionary path (basic to advanced) for an organization to do evaluation of SPI.
- Create awareness for taking into consideration confounding factors that might affect the accuracy and validity of the evaluation.

SPI-MEF Overview

Software Process Improvement Measurement And Evaluation Framework (SPI-MEF)

Key Concepts

implemented in

Stages

realized by

Steps

supported by

Support Artifacts

supported by

SPI-MEF Key Concepts

Purpose of this document:

The first two pages of this document describe the aims of SPI-MEF and give an overview of the framework as a whole. The remaining part tries to give a concise description of the key concepts of SPI-MEF such that sufficient background information about the framework is provided to the interviewees.

1. Measurement Levels and Viewpoints

- The measurement levels (Process, Project, Product, Organization, and External) represent the measurable entities which can be assessed to evaluate the software process improvement.
- SPI-MEF defines three generic viewpoints which represent the stakeholders who are interested to see the results of the improvement initiative.

By considering both measurement levels and viewpoints, the scope of the evaluation is defined (evaluation area), and serves as a driver for determining the appropriate measures.

Table 1: Example instance of an evaluation area

Measurement Levels	Viewpoints		
	Implementer	Coordinator	Sponsor
Process	Development team	SPI Coordinators, Process Managers	---
Project	Development team	Project Managers	---
Product	Project Managers	Product Managers	Head of Division
Organization	---	Board of Directors, SPI Steering Committee	Corporate SPI Sponsor, Shareholders
External	---	---	Corporate SPI Sponsor, Shareholders

2. Primary and Complementary Measures

- Primary measurements are the set of measurements which are used to assess if the improvement goal has been reached.
- Complementary measurements capture the effects of the process improvement which cannot be directly related to the improvement goal. They assess the potential side-effects caused by the improvement initiative.

Example:

SPI initiative:	Code inspection		
Improvement goal:	Improve product quality		
Measures:	Primary	Complementary	
Success indicator:	Defects (Quality)	Cost	Schedule
Metric:	Defect density	Effort in man-hours	Project cycle time

The “Iron Triangle” metaphor is used to illustrate the relationship between primary and complementary measurements and helps to derive the needed measures. The principle can be applied on every measurement level.

Process

Project

Product

Organization

External

3. Confounding Factors

Confounding factors represent a fundamental threat for the evaluation of a process improvement initiative if any kind of comparison is used to assess its effects. A comparison is said to be confounded if the observed difference between two values (the effect of a treatment) is not solely caused by the treatment alone but can be partially attributed to an external factor. The challenge in evaluating SPI initiatives is therefore to identify and possibly control confounding factors in order to achieve valid results. In this initial stage, SPI-MEF's aim is to create awareness of the potential threats caused by confounding factors and, since they are dependent on the context in which the improvement initiative is carried out, exemplify those which are most commonly encountered: project nature (new development, enhancement/maintenance), development model (Waterfall, Iterative models, etc.), product size, complexity and domain, employee factors (experience level, staff turnover) and technology related factors (programming language, tool support, etc.).

4. Derivation of measures for improvement evaluation

The previously introduced concepts provide additional information which facilitates the usage of the Goal-Question-Metric paradigm. SPI-MEF provides an interface with the conceptual level of GQM to define the appropriate measurement goals for improvement evaluation.

By using the input from SPI-MEF, it is possible to define very specific measurement goals which facilitate the elicitation of the appropriate questions. The following simple example shows how the concepts proposed by SPI-MEF interface with the GQM approach.

4.1 Information provided by SPI-MEF

Improvement Goal	Increase product quality
SPI Initiative	Code inspections
Target Entities	Project A, Product Z

Measurement Level	Viewpoints		
	Implementer	Coordinator	Sponsor
Process	---	Project Manager, SPI Process Coordinator	---
Project	Inspection Team	Project Manager, SPI Process Coordinator	---
Product	Project Manager	Product Manager, QA Manager	Head of Division
Organization	---	---	---
External	---	---	---

4.2 Interfaces between SPI-MEF and GQM

Business Goal	Increase product quality
Object of Study	Code inspection process
Purpose	Evaluate

Table 2: Example of interfaces between SPI-MEF and GQM

Measurement Levels		Focus	Point of View	Context
Process	MG1	Effectiveness	SPI Process Coordinator	Project A
	MG2*	Efficiency	Project Manager	Project A
	MG3*	Process conformance	SPI Process Coordinator	Project A
Project	MG4	Work product defects	Project Manager	Project A
	MG5	Work product defects	Inspection Team	Project A
	MG6*	Schedule	Project Manager	Project A
	MG7*	Effort	Project Manager	Project A
Product	MG8	Pre-release defects	Project Manager	Product Z
	MG9	Post-release defects	Product Manager	Product Z
	MG10*	Time-to-Market	Product Manager	Product Z
	MG11*	Cost	Product Manager	Product Z
	MG12*	Sales revenue	Product Manager	Product Z
	MG13	Sales revenue	Head of Division	Product Z
	MG14*	Cost	Head of Division	Product Z

Note: Measurement Goals (MG) with * are used to elicit complementary measurements.

4.3 Elaboration of Measurement Goals and Questions

In the following paragraphs a subset of the measurement goals presented in Table 2 are elaborated in more detail.

MG1: Primary Measurement Goal

Evaluate the process of code inspection with respect to its effectiveness on pre-test defect detection in Project A from the viewpoint of the SPI Process Coordinator.

Questions:

- What is the defect slippage of the used code inspection method?
- What is the severity distribution of the defects found during inspection?

MG2: Complementary Measurement Goal

Evaluate the process of code inspection with respect to its efficiency in Project A from the viewpoint of the Project Manager.

Questions:

- How many defects are found during the inspection activity?

MG3: Complementary Measurement Goal

Evaluate the process of code inspection with respect to its conformance to the specified standard process in Project A from the viewpoint of the SPI Process Coordinator.

Questions:

- Were the code inspections conducted according to the schedule (planned vs. conducted)?
- Were the participants appropriately prepared for the inspections (invitations and material distributed to the participants)?
- Were all the allocated participants present during the inspections (planned vs. actual participants)?

MG4: Primary Measurement Goal

Evaluate the effect of code inspection with respect to its impact on the quality of work products in Project A from the viewpoint of the Project Manager.

MG5: Primary Measurement Goal

Evaluate the effect of code inspection with respect to its impact on the quality of work products in Project A from the viewpoint of the Inspection Team.

5. Time to Evaluate

The determination of the appropriate time to evaluate the improvement is important; however it is difficult to suggest a general rule which is universally applicable. Therefore SPI-MEF introduces the concepts of Lag Factor and Degradation Factor which support the practitioner to determine the time-bounds for an improvement evaluation.

The Lag Factor is the minimum time required for the improvement initiative to propagate a visible impact on the measurable entities (measurement levels). The Degradation Factor, on the other hand, is the maximum time for which an evaluation result can be considered as valid, or, more specifically, can be considered as representing the actual status of the improvement.

The evaluation should be conducted within the interval defined by the Lag Factor and Degradation Factor. The figure below exemplifies the concept on the project, product and organization measurement levels.

Time to Evaluate

The only heuristic currently provided by SPI-MEF to determine the Lag Factor and Degradation Factor is that their values increase with the measurement levels, that is, $LF_{Proc} < LF_{Proj} < LF_{Prod} < LF_{Org} < LF_{Ext}$. Driven by these two factors, SPI-MEF proposes a periodic improvement evaluation, that is, an evaluation indexed by time to see the trend of the improvement.

6. Holistic View

The aim of the Holistic View is to provide a concise and crisp representation of the improvement evaluation results, taking into account measurement levels and viewpoints. The following components are used to construct the model:

- GL (Gain/Loss): To normalize the different measurements, their actual values are mapped to Gain (+1), Neutral (0) and Loss (-1), relative to previous evaluations.

- IR (Impact Rating): Each viewpoint (that is, each stakeholder of the improvement initiative) rates the impact of the improvement initiative on the respective measurement according to the following scale:

Impact assessment scale	Value
Low impact	1
Considerably low impact	2
Moderate impact	3
Considerably high impact	4
High impact	5

- SW (Subjective Weight): Each viewpoint gives a weight of subjective importance to every measurement. The weights sum up to 1.

From these components, the Subjective Value of Improvement (SVI) for each viewpoint is calculated as follows:

$$SVI_{vw} = \sum (GL_i * SW_i * IR_i) / n$$

vw: Sponsor / Coordinator / Implementer

i: Metric 1, Metric 2, , Metric n

n: Total number of metrics

The table below shows how SVI is calculated for measurements at the process level. The Average Value of Improvement (AVI) is the arithmetic mean of SVI.

Table 2: Example of SVI calculation at the process level

Viewpoint	Metrics	Gain / Loss ^{GL}	Subjective Weight ^{SW}	Impact rating ^{IR}	Subjective Value of Improvement ^{SVI}
Sponsor	M1	1	0.4	3	[(1)(0.4)(3) + (-1)(0.6)(4)] / 2 = -0.60
	M2	-1	0.6	4	
Coordinator	M2	-1	0.3	5	[(-1)(0.3)(5) + (1)(0.2)(5) + (1)(0.5)(4)] / 3 = 0.50
	M3	1	0.2	5	
	M4	1	0.5	4	
Implementer	M3	1	0.5	4	[(1)(0.5)(4) + (-1)(0.5)(0)] / 2 = 1.00
	M5	-1	0.5	0	
Average Value of Improvement ^{AVI} :					(-0.50 + 0.20 + 0.75) / 3 = 0.90

Holistic View of Improvement

By calculating the AVI for each evaluated measurement level, the overall improvement can be represented in a radar (Kiviat) diagram as shown in the above figure.

7. Evaluation Opportunity Matrix

SPI-MEF proposes an opportunity matrix to guide organizations towards a holistic improvement evaluation. This opportunity matrix is realized by considering the accuracy of the measurements and coverage of the evaluation. The accuracy of the measurements is determined by the usage of primary and complementary measures, cross examination measures and considering confounding factors when selecting the measurement and conducting the evaluation. Cross examination assesses a particular success indicator by using more than one measure in order to increase the confidence level in the validity of the evaluation.

The coverage of evaluation is determined by the extent to which measurement levels and viewpoints are included in conducting the evaluation. The figure below illustrates the opportunity matrix. Organizations shall position their current state of evaluation quality using gap analysis considering the accuracy and coverage illustrated in the opportunity matrix. Then the opportunity matrix will help to highlight areas of improvement towards achieving a holistic evaluation.

